

EMOTIONAL MATURITY AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN RELATION TO THEIR GENDER AND TYPE OF SCHOOL

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Abstract

Emotional maturity means right decision taken in a right time in a right manner. We observe in our environment and surroundings, emotional maturity is very vital to all inhabitants for living with peace and harmony in their life. The current study intended to identify the emotional maturity among secondary school students in relation to their gender and type of school. The sample consists of 200 school students of private and government school. Out of which 100 were from private school students and 100 from government. The data was collected from Mandi District of Himachal Pradesh. Emotional Maturity Scale (EMS) developed by the researcher was used for data collection. Mean, SD & t-test were used for data analysis. The findings revealed that there exists no significant difference in emotional maturity of male and female students but students from private and government school shows a significant difference in their emotional maturity. The study revealed that the students who studying in private schools are emotionally more matured as comparison to students belonging to government school.

Keywords: *Emotional Maturity, Type of School, Government, Private, Gender*

Introduction

The noble aim of education is all-round development of an individual. To become an ideal, well-rounded, successful & competitive citizens of a community, every child should be developed with the necessary life skill. Besides other numerous factors related with human life, an emotion is also a vital factor. Emotional development of a child is very necessary because without emotions a human being is like a robot. An emotionally mature

person can adjust in any circumstances and handle every situation in a peaceful way with suitable decision as we needed. In present scenario everyone is extremely aggressive to show better than others. In these circumstances, students are facing difficulties and rise to many problems such as anxiety, tensions, frustrations and emotional upsets in everyday life. With this competitive society people are moving faster to achieve the best many times which leads towards the frustrations in case of failure. And this frustration occurs due to the lack of proper emotional maturity. Emotional maturity is most demanding attribute in present scenario as it helps a person to be self-aware, positive, kindhearted, flexible and responsible to face the complexities of life in a peaceful and flexible way. Emotional maturity can also help individual's growth and development in all manners such as social and mental. Thus, major aim of a good education must be to help learners gain emotional maturity. Emotional maturity develops throughout the life. When we think about 'maturity', the first thing that comes to mind is usually the 'age'. However, when it comes to emotional maturity, the age of a person is not always an exact sign. **Woodworth** in Mangal, S.K. (2007) (pp. 94) stated that "emotion is a 'moved' or 'stirred-up state of an organism. It is a stirred-up state of feeling that is the way it appears to the individual himself. It is a disturbed muscular and glandular activity that is the way it appears to an external observer". **Crow and Crow** in Mangal, S.K. (2007) (pp.94) explored that "emotion is an affective experience that accompanies generalized linear adjustment and mental and physiological stirred-up states in the individual and that shows itself in his overt behavior". Further, **Charles G. Morris** in Mangal, S.K. (2007) (pp.94) defined that "emotion is a complex affective experience that involves diffuse physiological changes and can be expressed overtly in characteristic behavior patterns". In the light of these definitions we can say that emotional maturity is one of the important aspects of individual's behavior.

Emotional maturity among adolescents plays a vital role for development of their individuality. Moreover, in order to lead a healthy life in society, there is a great need for proper development of the adolescents' emotional maturity. A person, who cannot properly develop a positive response to emotional maturity he/she cannot be considered as a perfect individual. In such a situation, emotional maturity has needed to adapt to the norms of behavior for develop a good human being. Subramanian and Veliappan (2013) found that the high school students belonging to private schools are emotionally more mature. Yashotha and Karnan (2017) showed a significant relationship between emotional maturity and decision making of high school students. Their finding revealed that there is significant association

between emotional maturity of high school students with respect to gender and type of family. Majumdar and Das (2019) found that the government school students have more emotional maturity than private school students. It means types of school plays a major role to develop the emotional maturity; secondary girl students have more emotional maturity than the secondary boy students. Sharma and Singh (2022) revealed that there is no significance difference in emotional competence of males and females senior secondary school students. In the light of above findings the researcher conducted present investigation to check whether there exists any difference of emotional maturity among secondary school students in relation to their gender and type of school? Following objectives were framed to get the answer.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the emotional maturity of secondary school students in relation to their gender.
2. To study the emotional maturity of secondary school students in relation to their type of school.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. There will be no significant difference in emotional maturity of secondary school students in relation to their gender.
2. There will be no significant difference in emotional maturity of secondary school students in relation to their type of school.

Variables of the study

In this study Emotional Maturity is dependent variable and Gender and Type of School are independent variable.

Sample of the study

In the present study, investigator has selected sample of 200 secondary school students from Mandi District of Himachal Pradesh. Simple random sampling method used for data collection.

Tool Used

Emotional Maturity Scale developed by investigator herself.

Methodology

Survey method is used by the researcher under descriptive research.

Results

The first objective of the present investigation is to study the emotional maturity of secondary school students in relation to their gender. To find out the difference in emotional

maturity of secondary school students in relation to their gender, the emotional maturity score of the male and female students were calculated and 't' test was employed. 't' value showing significance of difference in mean scores of secondary school students in relation to their gender and type of school are shown in table-1

Table- 1
't' Value Showing Significance of Difference in Mean Scores of Secondary School Students in relation to their Gender

S.No	Gender	Number	Mean	SD	't'
1	Male	100	141.51	18.13	0.68 NS
2	Female	100	139.67	19.62	

NS- Non-Significant at 0.05 Level

Table-1 presented that calculated 't' value turned out to be 0.68 which is less than table value 1.97 even at 0.05 level of significant. Hence **Hypothesis no. 1 that "There will be no significant difference in emotional maturity of secondary school students in relation to their gender" is accepted.** It reveals that there exists no significant difference in emotional maturity of secondary school students in relation to their gender. Table 1 also supports a negligible difference in the mean value of the emotional maturity score among male and female secondary school students.

The second objective in this investigation is to study the emotional maturity of secondary school students in relation to their type of school. To find out the difference in emotional maturity of secondary school students studying in government and private schools, 't' test was employed to analyze the difference. The results are shown in table-2

Table 2
't' Value Showing Significant Difference in Mean Scores of Secondary School Students in relation to Type of School

S.No	Type of School	Number	Mean	SD	't'
1	Government	100	134.47	18.32	3.40 **
2	Private	100	143.12	17.55	

**** Significant at 0.01 level**

The calculated 't' value shown in table-2 came out to be 3.40 which is greater than the table value 2.59 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence **Hypothesis no. 2 "There will be no significant difference in emotional maturity of secondary school students in relation to their type of school" is rejected.** It reveals that there exists a significant difference in

emotional maturity of secondary school students who studying in government and private schools. Table -2 further shows a difference in mean score of the emotional maturity. It is higher (143.12) for private secondary school students as compared to government secondary school students i.e. (134.47). From this it can be interpreted that secondary school students who studying in private schools are emotionally more matured as comparison to those who studying in government schools. Figure-1 shows the significant difference in ‘emotional maturity’ of secondary school students belonging to government and private schools

Figure-1

Difference in ‘Emotional Maturity’ of Secondary School Students belonging to Government and Private Schools

Suggestion

1. Government and management should organize special workshops, lecture, guidance and counseling programme for both male and female students so that they may discuss their problems and causes of dissatisfaction with their mentor.
2. Parents and teacher play a major role in inculcating emotional stability and decision making power among students as which is essential for their academic and professional growth. So, special workshops, lecture, guidance and counseling programme must be organized for the teachers and parents too.
3. Important life skills like decision making, coping with stress, coping with emotions must be taught in early stages of schooling.
4. Individual differences must be adequately handled in early stages of life.
5. Home as well as school environment must be democratic.

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